

MODERN DIDACTIC REQUIREMENTS FOR THE PERSONALITY OF A PEDAGOGIC TEACHER

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***Annotation:** A professional teacher is the only person who devotes most of his time to teaching and raising student. The rest of the adults, including the student's parents, are busy with their professional problems and household chores and cannot devote much time to student. If teachers had not been involved in the education and upbringing of student, then after a few generations' society would have stopped developing. The new generation of people would simply be insufficiently prepared to support social, economic and cultural progress. In a modern civilized society, a teacher is a figure that requires special attention, and where his place is taken by insufficiently trained people, student suffer first of all, and the losses that arise here are usually irreparable. This requires society to create conditions so that teachers and educators include people who are most intellectually and morally prepared to work with student, and not everyone can do this.*

***Keywords:** sociability, pedagogical decision, optimism*

All these properties are not innate. They are acquired through systematic and hard work, and the teacher's tremendous work on himself. It is no coincidence that there are many teachers and educators, but there are only a few gifted and talented among them who brilliantly cope with all their duties. Additional but relatively stable requirements for a teacher are sociability, artistry, cheerful disposition, good taste, and others. These qualities are important, but less so than the main ones listed above. A teacher or educator can do without each of these qualities individually... The main and secondary pedagogical qualities together make up the individuality of

the teacher, by virtue of which every good teacher is a unique and peculiar personality.

List of specific (professional) qualities of a teacher (teacher, educator):

1. Pedagogical erudition is a stock of knowledge used by a teacher to solve pedagogical problems.

2. Pedagogical goal setting is the teacher's need for planning pedagogical activities and willingness to change tasks depending on the pedagogical situation.

3. Pedagogical thinking is a special component of a teacher's professional competence, which consists in the ability to compare and classify situations, to detect cause-and-effect relationships in them. Pedagogical thinking includes practical, diagnostic, analytical, discursive (expanded in time) thinking.

4. Pedagogical intuition is a feature that determines why it is necessary to act this way, to do it, and not otherwise. Pedagogical intuition contributes to the simultaneous adoption of a pedagogical decision, taking into account the anticipation of the further development of the situation without a detailed, informed analysis.

5. Pedagogical improvisation is the finding of an unexpected pedagogical solution and its instant implementation, which includes the stages:

a) pedagogical insight;

b) instant comprehension and choice of the way of realization of the idea;

c) public implementation and realization of the pedagogical idea;

d) comprehension and decision on the continuation of improvisation or its completion.

6. Pedagogical observation, vigilance - understanding the essence of the pedagogical situation based on external minor signs and details.

7. Pedagogical optimism is the ability to find positive and positive things in an activity.

8. Pedagogical resourcefulness is the ability to rebuild a difficult pedagogical situation and convey a positive emotional tone to it.

9. Pedagogical forecasting is the ability to anticipate a student's reaction and behavior before or towards the end of a pedagogical situation.

10. Pedagogical reflection is the ability to consciously analyze oneself. Reflection is the teacher's independent approach to introspection.

11. Pedagogical self-awareness (as a property) or a set of teacher's ideas about himself as a professional includes the following components:

a) awareness of the norms, rules and models of one's professional activity, when the standards of a professional worldview are formed;

b) awareness of these qualities in other teachers, comparing oneself with others;

c) taking into account the assessment of oneself as a professional by other people (looking at oneself through the eyes of others);

d) self-assessment of their individual sides of their personality:

- understanding and self-awareness; - emotional attitude and evaluation;

The social significance of pedagogical work determines the high demands on the teacher's personality. Since ancient times, society has entrusted its future - student - to the most experienced, wise, and highly moral people. High moral character is a necessary quality of a teacher's personality, as the teacher gives moral lessons to his students every day. Therefore, a cynic, a morally unscrupulous person should not be a teacher. "The influence of the educator's personality on the young soul is an educational force that cannot be replaced by textbooks, moral maxims, or a system of punishments and rewards," emphasized K. D. Ushinsky. The necessary arsenal of personal qualities of a teacher is responsibility, conscientiousness, diligence, pedagogical justice (the moral quality of the teacher and the assessment of the measure of his impact on students, corresponding to their real merits to the team). The teacher, first of all, evaluates his own activity and its results, therefore it

is very important that this assessment be unbiased and objective. According to Ya. A. Komensky, "teachers should be people...They are honest, active and hardworking; not only in appearance, but in fact, they should be living examples of the virtues that they should instill in others." Of all the moral qualities, love for student is the most essential for a teacher. This requirement for the teacher's personality can be found in the works of every outstanding teacher, however, the teacher V. A. Sukhomlinsky said it best: "What does a good teacher mean? This is, first of all, a person who loves student, finds joy in communicating with them, believes that every child can become a good person, knows how to be friends with student, takes student's joys and sorrows to heart, knows the soul of a child, never forgets that he himself was a child." Love for student alone does not determine the success of teaching activities. We need certain personality qualities that ensure success in teaching - pedagogical abilities.

All types of interaction are interconnected: cooperation and dialogue have great educational opportunities, but in a particular situation, some students may need custody, attention and care, some have established business relationships based on an agreement, and strict requirements are justified for someone at the moment, that is It is necessary to take into account the specific conditions when choosing the optimal type of interaction. All systems of interaction (between teachers and students, between teachers and parents, between teachers) are interconnected and influence each other. The interaction of teachers and students plays a crucial role. At the same time, the style of relationship between teachers and student, teachers and parents depends on the nature of the relationship in the teaching staff. The success of pedagogical interaction depends on the level of the teacher's communicative culture, which is based on sociability (a steady desire for contacts with people, the ability to quickly establish contacts) and the level of moral education of the teacher (tact, attention to the opinions and suggestions of the other side, respect for each other's position, empathy, empathy).

One of the most socially significant humanistic professions is that of a teacher, whose activities are aimed at the development and formation of a person. According to A.N.Leontiev's theory, the main thing that distinguishes this activity from others is the subject it is aimed at. The uniqueness of pedagogical activity lies in its subject, the object of work - the developing personality of a pupil, a student who is in constant changes, the nature of which is determined by the position of the teacher. Since ancient times, society has entrusted its student's future to the most experienced, wise, and highly moral people. High moral character is a necessary quality of a teacher's personality, as the teacher gives moral lessons to his students every day. Therefore, a cynic, a morally unscrupulous person should not be a teacher. "The influence of the educator's personality on the young soul is an educational force that cannot be replaced by textbooks, moral maxims, or a system of punishments and rewards," emphasized K. D. Ushinsky. At the current stage of society's development, there is a question of training an "effective teacher" who is able to provide a high level of education in conditions of mass education, to take qualified care of students' health and leisure. In order to meet modern increased requirements, a teacher must constantly replenish his knowledge of a general cultural and professional nature, work with considerable effort, dedication, and take high responsibility for his actions. Love for student alone does not determine the success of teaching activities. We need certain personality qualities that ensure success in teaching - pedagogical abilities.

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